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ZAMONAVIY DUNYONING IJTIMOIY MANZARASI VA JAMIYAT TUZILMALARI TRANSFORMATSIYASI

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2. MINTAQAHOLISI QADRIYATLARINING DINAMIKASI
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4. ZAMONAVIY DUNYO IJTIMOIY MANZARASINING TRANSFORMATSIYALASHUVI

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ZAMONAVIY DUNYONING IJTIMOIY MANZARASI VA JAMIYAT TUZILMALARI TRANSFORMATSIYASI

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RESEARCH IN SOCIOLOGY OF SPORTS IN INDIA AND POSSIBILITIES FOR THE WORLD

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Abstract: This paper focuses on the state of Sociology of Sport in India, a country with a population of 1.3 billion and a sport culture that seems to show particular characteristics, but remains relatively under-researched. This could offer an abundance of opportunities for Indian scholars, as well as foreign ones. The objective of the paper is to reveal some of these specificities of the Indian context, relying on the conceptual work of researchers from Europe and other parts of Asia such as China, Japan, South Korea and Taiwan. One of the issues to be discussed is the attitudes of parents towards sport as a recreational activity and as a prospect of career growth. Another concern, which requires investigation, is the place of sport in the public education system, which puts much more emphasis on academic subjects at the expense of physical education. All of these features of the Indian sport culture hinder the participation of youth in sport and physical activity, and, to address this challenge, the paper aims to identify the potential priorities of a sport sociological research agenda in India. With this background, it is trusted that this piece shall contribute towards a better understanding of the sociological factors which can be instrumental in the promotion of sports and physical culture, the development of youth and the nation.

We are hopeful that this may reflect an increasingly vibrant research culture in these countries, and of immense benefit to the Indian scholarly fraternity, specifically "Sports Sociologists". Indeed, the tradition of social scientific research into sport is more established in the Far West than in other Asian regions. At this juncture, we hope that this study stimulates academic curiosity about social, political and economic implications of sport in the wider Asia-Europe region. This research is basically premised on Sociology of Sports in India and the developments, with a research base of two states of India, for prospects of Researchers from the Western world.

Keywords: India, sociology, sports, youth, development, integration, Western World

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ СОЦИОЛОГИИ СПОРТА В ИНДИИ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ДЛЯ МИРА

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Аннотация: Эта статья сосредоточена на состоянии социологии спорта в Индии - стране с населением 1,3 миллиарда человек и культурой спорта, которая, кажется, обладает особыми характеристиками, но остается относительно малоисследованной. Это может предоставить обилие возможностей для индийских ученых, а также иностранных. Цель статьи - раскрыть некоторые из этих особенностей индийского контекста, опираясь на концептуальную работу исследователей из Европы и других частей Азии, таких как Китай, Япония, Южная Корея и Тайвань. Одной из проблем, которую следует обсудить, являются отношения родителей к спорту как к рекреационной деятельности и перспективе карьерного роста. Еще одной проблемой, требующей исследования, является место спорта в общественной системе образования, которая уделяет гораздо больше внимания академическим предметам в ущерб физическому воспитанию. Все эти особенности индийской спортивной культуры препятствуют участию молодежи в спорте и физической активности, и для решения этой проблемы статья стремится определить потенциальные приоритеты спортивной социологической исследовательской повестки дня в Индии. Исходя из этого, мы надеемся, что эта работа способствует лучшему пониманию социологических факторов, которые могут способствовать продвижению спорта и физической культуры, развитию молодежи и нации.

Мы надеемся, что это отражает все более живую исследовательскую культуру в этих странах, и будет иметь огромную пользу для индийских ученых, особенно исследователей в социологии спорта. Действительно, традиция социально-научных исследований спорта более развита на Западе, чем в других регионах Азии. На данном этапе мы надеемся, что данное исследование стимулирует академический интерес относительно социальных, политических и экономических последствий спорта в более широком Азиатско-европейском регионе. Это исследование в основном базируется на социологии спорта в Индии и разработках, с исследовательской базой в двух штатах Индии, для перспектив исследователей из Западного мира.

Ключевые слова: Индия, социология, спорт, молодежь, развитие, интеграция, Западный мир.

Over the past decade, UN agencies, international sport federations, international and national non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and national governments have been using sport as a tool for development. The crucial rationale that can be attributed to this belief is documented from studies that under appropriate conditions physical health benefits of sport such as prevention of diseases, lessening of likelihood of unhealthy practices (such as illegal drug use and unsafe sex), potential to positively influence social integration and inclusion of people with disabilities, women and girls, enhancement of self-worth and the likes contribute to the social fabric of our society. The level of development of a Nation which was initially considered only in economic terms limiting itself to dependence on industrial, agricultural and/or service sectors, is witnessing a paradigm shift. The idea that well-being of a country only on the pretext of economic growth was challenged by the United Nation's Declaration on the Right of Development (1986):

Development is a comprehensive economic, social, cultural and political process, which aims at the constant improvement of the well-being of the entire population and of all individuals on the basis of their active, free and meaningful participation in development and the fair distribution of benefits there from.

As I intend to study the sociological perspective of sport through which the development mechanism can be generated, it would be appropriate to apprehend it in a broader sense. This field should be concerned with the descriptions and explanations of the interrelations between sports and

other social components...the unique feature about the sociological approach to sport, as distinct that from psychology has been a focus about sport in its function as a component of social organization (Edwards, Harry: 1973) The sociological perception of sports is based on three fundamental themes; sport is a social institution worthy of sociological examination like the more traditional institutions of politics, religion, economy, marriage/family, law, health/medicine education, and science; sport is a microcosm of the larger society and as such reflects and reinforces the foremost philosophy; and several institutional links between sport and other societal institutions make it impossible for changes in one sphere not to have deep effects in all spheres. Methodological considerations of Bourdieu and Giddens's render the current research as discursive construction of social practices. Bourdieu's social approach to the study of sport, the sub discipline of Sport Sociology, and the scope it offers to those inquiring into the social dimensions of sport and physical education have been widely recognized (Clement, 1995; Jarvie & McGuire, 1994; De France, 1995). His sociology has inspired many publications on 'sport studies' (Clement, 1995) and Clement (1995) and argues that it is the relevance of the bodily dimensions (which I talk of as the mind set) of sport that makes Bourdieu's approach attractive. He does not offer a social set of principles as much as a sociological method and a set of analytical tools through which culture and society can be understood and examined. His notion of habitus in particular, suggests a means of understanding how bodily engagement in day to day practice and in the practice of sport and other institutionalized physical activity function to symbolize the interacting dynamics of culture, class and gender. However, when I try to collaborate Giddens structuration with what I intend to do, I do find a symmetry. The structuration approach does not focus on the individual actor or societal totality but social practices ordered across space and time. Agency, as Giddens calls, is human action. To be human is to be an agent, although not all agents are human beings. The agency, according to Giddens, can lead to both the reproduction and the transformation of society. Practices are produced in a context of the duality of structure and agency (Rob Stones, 2005, Structuration Theory, pp.4-5) and are not themselves simply agency. It is the practices that reproduce social structures and these social structures can develop the mind set of the very vast populace of India, in particular the youth, by absorbing and driving them in to the main stream of national development. With the given potential and India developing as a youth nation in the forth coming 15 years, there are dream projects by which I intend to draw schedule as to why we have still to move ahead in this area of sports, despite that other big nations are already on the pace of development far more than us.

In this paper, centered around Sociology of Sports literature, scholars based in Europe including other parts of Asia, will be getting an insight and in the process possibilities of further research in this area. This is withstanding of the fact that India is a vast populace of over 130 billion, and chances for Academicians galore. We are hopeful that this may reflect an increasingly vibrant research culture in these countries, and of immense benefit to the Indian scholarly fraternity, specifically "Sports Sociologists". This paper is basically premised on Sociology of Sports in India and the developments, with a research base of two states of India, for prospects of Researchers from the European Union and other parts of Asia.

Importance of this study and Objectives

In most developing nations today, young people make up the largest segment of the population — in some cases more than 50%. In most cases, the number of young people will peak in the next 10 years, in some cases in the next 20 years. This means that countries will be facing significant fiscal pressures to fund secondary education and the prevention of non-communicable and infectious diseases such as HIV and AIDS. The large number of young people also offers an historic opportunity. The emerging workforce is young, and the overall population contains relatively few elderly individuals and children to support. For governments, this can free up resources to invest in things like human capital that yield high development returns. To maximize the opportunity this young cohort presents, it is important to invest in and support today's children and youth. Investing in children and youth today will ensure that they are healthy and well equipped to manage the critical life transitions ahead of them. The World Bank has identified five components of because it involves

youth development, or transitions, that have a major impact on how each young person's human capital is safeguarded, developed and deployed:

- Continuing to learn;
- Starting to work;
- Developing a healthy lifestyle;
- Beginning a family; and
- Exercising citizenship.

The importance of this proposed topic can be readily gauged by the global attention it has been receiving for the past some years, and this importance has increased vigorously at least during the past two decades.

These commitments reinforce the importance of sport and play as a basic human right for all children and youth. Sport can add significantly to global, national and local efforts to give children a healthy start. Sport can help those who haven't received a good start, and equip youth with the information, skills, personal and social resources, and support needed to make key life transitions successfully. It is important to note, however, that much of the facts supporting sport's potential come from developed countries. However, sport is already being used worldwide to advance child and youth development and education, suggesting that its benefits are already appreciated, if not yet fully understood or explained.

However, the sports culture in India is one prime issue which needs to be analyzed. The sociological mindset of parents towards sports which visualizes it only as a recreational activity (that too in very less number of cases) and not as a career growth prospect, the educational curriculum which puts more emphasis on academics leaving behind sports are some of the concerns which require investigation. Research directed at the relationship between parents and their children is important in that the behavior and approach of parents may impact the players' desire to continue playing sports. With this background, it is trusted that this study shall contribute towards a better understanding of the sociological factors which can be instrumental in promotion of sports, development of the youth and the nation.

Literature Review

By naming 2005 The International Year of Sport and Physical Education, the United Nations did much to broaden the analysis of sport, and child and youth development, globally, and to increase the acceptance of sport as both an end and a means to aspects of international development, such as the Millennium Development Goals (Van Eekeren, 2006, p.19). Although much of the literature reviewed in this document uses definitions, concepts and evidence from high-income countries, a great deal of international attention is being paid to the potential utility of sport for child and youth development in Lower Middle Income Countries (LMICs). Recently, scholars have argued for the need to conduct prolonged, critical and empirical analyses of the utility of sport for child and youth development in LMICs, although this literature is only now emerging, and evidence of the success (or failure) of sport and child/youth development interventions in LMICs is scarce at this time (Auweele et al., 2006, p.15).

With context to India, there is almost no research work done in this area, particularly with reference to the sociological measurements pertaining to growth and development of the children and youth through sports practices. As such, reliance on a single type or source of data (statistics, case profiles, and interviews with stakeholders and/or participants) will fail to capture the complexities of the relationship between sport and child/youth development and many studies need to be reflected upon, apart from evidence-based research.

According to Peter Donnelly & Simon Darnell, University of Toronto, and Jay Coakley from University of Colorado in their report on the use of sport to foster child and youth development and education, 2007:

“With regard to all of the other benefits of participation in sport identified in the research literature (i.e., psychological and social benefits and improved mental health), the evident benefits appear to be an indirect outcome of the context and social interaction that is possible in sport rather than a direct outcome of participating in sport. Critical analysis of a broad range of research findings

provides overwhelming support for this conclusion. The research is often carried out under the assumption that positive benefits result from sport, or with the intention of discovering the positive benefits resulting from sport. As pointed out in the reviews, and in a number of critical meta-analyses that were reviewed, the results of such ‘research’ are frequently taken up uncritically, and repeated in other literatures. As a consequence of the above finding, two major areas of further research are needed:

Research to add to our growing knowledge of the precise circumstances under which sport may result in positive outcomes for gender relations, disability inclusion, youth development, mental health, peace and conflict resolution, and other areas of interest; research concerning how sport may be adapted to achieve positive outcomes in different contexts, and for different populations and individuals; and research that assists program organizers to determine and plan the specific aims and form of the intervention.

o Research on leadership and leadership training – the form of leadership, and the knowledge and training of leaders have frequently been identified in the research literature as key to the achievement of positive benefits as a result of sport participation”.

Donnelly, Peter in *Sport and Social Theory*, 2007 observes:

The relationship between social class and participation in sport and physical activity is much more complex than it is possible to explain by either agency or structure interpretations alone. Individuals do choose whether to participate or not, if the circumstances of their lives permit such a choice. And even if the choice is available to an individual, a whole host of circumstances from that person’s past (e.g. whether his/her family had been involved in sport, or had encouraged participation; the person’s experiences in school physical education classes, etc.) and present (e.g. whether transportation and child care are available; whether they are safe; whether people are made to feel welcome and comfortable participating) may affect his/her decision.

Donnelly and Harvey (1996: 23–4) outline the structural barriers to participation in sport and physical activity, which they classify as:

(1) Infrastructural barriers – associated with the material means of access (e.g. cost, available transportation, time, etc.);

(2) Super structural barriers – associated with ideas about access (e.g. policies, knowledge, prejudice, etc.); and

(3) Procedural barriers – associated with the course of action available to individuals to attain access (e.g. social support, citizens’ rights, organizational structure and management style).

Donnelly characterized that ‘a fully democratized sport and leisure environment [which] include(s) both the right to participate, regardless of one’s particular set of social characteristics, and the right to be involved in determination of the forms, circumstances and meanings of participation’ (1993: 417). In other words, the agency of participants is involved in creating and recreating the structural circumstances of their participation.

Research Methodology

The factors that influence sports participation have emerged as a point of interest among many academics and policy-makers (Wheeler, Sharon; 2011). In order to detect the determinants of sports participation, a constructive and exploratory research methodology has been adopted by me. My academic pursuits in the field of Sociology, coupled with my distinctions in the field of sports as a National Technical Official of the Athletics Federation of India have helped me in making an empirical study, the base for which has been the interview methodology.

The data drawn upon in the present study has a sample size of 500 interviews, spread over the two big States of Uttar Pradesh (U.P.) and Bihar. 350 interviews have been conducted from Uttar Pradesh and 150 interviews from Bihar. The States of U.P. and Bihar had been chosen due to reasons of their population percentile (U.P. being the most populated and Bihar the third most populated state of India) (Census, India 2011), and due to their lagging behind in the human index of development. A choice of these states helped me in assessing the virtual impact of sociological development through sports. Geographically, districts (both empowered and underpowered were selected) from both the states were selected for interviewing, so as to get a mix of the sample and spatial classification method

was used. Urban, Semi-urban and rural areas were given due consideration in my study, so as to make it more pragmatic and meaningful. For each interview, the questionnaire was bifurcated. The first part imbibed questions which were put up to the parents of the children (students) and the other part for the children (students). The age group of students interviewed ranged from 15 to 24 years. Prior to this, the first phase considered data collection for recruitment of families. Before going for the interview, the parents and children were briefed regarding the nature and purpose of the study. Some initial questions relating to interviewee's sporting habits, what sports they ever did, or what sports will they be doing, how often they did these sports, who with, where they did them, and how they become involved in them were common to both. Furthermore, both interviews included questions regarding the parents' behaviors and beliefs in relation to the child's sports participation, thus shedding light on the children's socialization into sport. Children's sports activities, their schoolings, hobbies, interests towards other social activities, their inclination towards sports and which sport in particular, facilities in their schools or colleges and back at home, availability of telecommunication facilities such as mobile phones, internet etc., their experiences after playing, their level of satisfaction at the end of the day after playing, etc. were recorded. Gender consideration was given while interviewing the children. The parents interview scheduling consisted of their occupations, socio-economic background, whether they too hail from a sportive cultural background, and if yes, then whether they have tried to provide opportunities for their children, their views about national and international sports events and inclinations, their opinion about sport as a sociological tool for their children's development and growth, or sport as a leisure time activity, sport as a career objective, sport as a feel of patriotism, role of government in promoting sports, etc. Some interviews were recorded also. Marks in a point scale from 0 to 100 in groups of 0-10, 10-20, 20-30...were assigned for each question thereby quantitatively classifying the data. Frequency distribution was ascertained thereafter.

The questionnaire, containing 50 questions were designed with the help of senior luminaries in the field of sports, such as the Secretary and Joint Secretary of Athletics Federation of India, some Cricket coaches, Kabaddi coaches, etc. as this could have helped in designing the most pertinent questions. From the field of Sociology, I consulted some eminent Sociologists in order to ensure that the sociological aspect of development is being purely looked into. A Pre-Testing was done on four to five sets of parents and students and this helped me in knowing the shortcomings, drawbacks, costing, timings etc., and I incorporated the corrections in the interview questionnaire. Statistical tools were applied to derive the results.

Results & Conclusion. The significant effects of various factors imminent to the development aspect through this Sociological study were investigated. The summary tables statistically for various levels with brief discussions are being produced here below:-

Table 1. The Socio-economic back grounds of parent's vis-à-vis inclination towards sports

Income bracket Annually (INR)* (in %)	State of UP	State of Bihar	Inclination/Sports	
			U.P.	Bihar
38,000 – 50,000	73	23	21	16
50,000 – 75,000	174	69	28	27
75,000 – 1,00,000	58	33	29	25
1,00,000 – 1,25,000	45	25	27	24

*As per the latest index (of 2012) of the Planning Commission, Government of India, the annual income of an average Indian comes to INR 36,500. This had been the basic criteria behind starting with an income bracket of INR 38,000.

It has been analyzed that the inclination of parents given their socio-economic background towards putting their children in sports activities shows a declining trend (i.e.27% and 24% in the 1 – 1.25 lac bracket) in both the States. The meager enhancement of 1% (i.e. 29% in 0.75 – 1 lac bracket) in the State of U.P. but again a dip in the same bracket in Bihar shows the disinclination. The

overall percentage of inclination of the parents, who had been thoroughly questioned, is dismal. The mindset of these parents towards sports and social development is read as less impacting. The proletariat class suffers.

Table 2. Socio-Cultural back grounds of parent's vis-à-vis inclination towards sports

Income bracket Annually (INR)	State of UP	State of Bihar	Inclination/Sports	
			U.P.	Bihar (in %)
38,000 – 50,000	73	23	19	14
50,000 – 75,000	174	69	32	25
75,000 – 1,00,000	58	33	34	23
1,00,000 – 1,25,000	45	25	35	25

The Socio-Cultural scenario is somewhat different, with some healthy factors. The parents were discussed about their social and cultural backgrounds, with not only sports but regarding participation in other co-curricular activities, such as indoor games, meetings in societies, attending panchayats, fairs, exhibitions, traditional dancing, singing and other such activities which make them and their children more vibrant and active. The results at Table 2 show that with the rise of income level, the inclination towards cultural activities and sports does increase.

Table 3. Impact of geographical location

Income bracket Annually (INR)	State of UP	State of Bihar	Inclination/Sports	
			U.P.	Bihar (in %)
38,000 – 50,000	73	23	36	11
50,000 – 75,000	174	69	39	13
75,000 – 1,00,000	58	33	41	14
1,00,000 – 1,25,000	45	25	46	17

The observations given by the respondents establish that geographical location plays a vital role towards educating the mindset of the people. It is evident that the state of Uttar Pradesh takes lead in comparison to the state of Bihar. It was assessed that the per capita income of the state of UP is higher in relation to Bihar. Moreover, the various districts covered in the state of UP, pose the advantage that people take over. A good geographical location, which envisages the desired infra structure, helps in aiding and enhancing the outlook of the parents and children/youth both. The parents informed that the availability of infra structure somewhat incited them to send their children to playgrounds. However, in the state of Bihar, despite the less percentile in comparison to UP, we observe that there is increase in the percentage and involvement, and this goes to establish somewhat that geographical location does play a role in changing social awareness and belongingness towards sports.

Table 4. Female participation factor influencing sports

Income bracket Annually (INR)	State of UP	State of Bihar	Inclination/Sports	
			U.P.	Bihar
		(Women in %)		
38,000 – 50,000(12%)	73	23	29	22
50,000 – 75,000(14%)	174	69	36	25
75,000 – 1,00,000(16%)	58	33	41	29
1,00,000 – 1,25,000(21%)	45	25	53	31

Observations on gender participation were heartening. Out of the income brackets shown, the percentile of women increases with the enhancement of income. It were the women which had been interviewed, and they were of the opinion that sports does change the mindset of children and youth. They compared sports with the physical work which they were doing at home, and stated that this keeps them mentally and physically healthy. Naturally, the increase in income level provided them with more able opportunities. However, it was informed that female participation was less in comparison to male, and many factors such as environment, economic background, etc. were attributed, besides the male hierarchical approach.

Expected contribution of the research

The potentials that exist within sport are those that can help with fundamentally different views of the world perhaps based upon opportunities to encourage trust, obligations, redistribution and respect for sport in a more socially orientated humanitarian world. While it is important to explain and understand economic, social, historical, physiological, psychological and many other explanations of what sport can do for society, the more significant intellectual and practical questions often originate from questions relating to social change (Jarvie, Grant 2007). To ignore the capacity of sport to assist with social change is not an option, particularly for students, teachers and researchers of sport, all of whom have the capacity and the platform to act as public intellectuals. It is for the first time that this research stresses the importance of human beings in sport rather than sport itself. Thus, alongside vigorous economic and social reform, Indian sports policy will be encouraged to undergo a substantial change. The contribution which I intend to deliver to the policy makers and educationists is as follows:

1. Despite the growing number of actors and actions promoting sporting activity, it remains true that few of the young people are used to sports practices in India. To address the use of sports practices by the children and youth and inculcate a habit of indulging in to physical activities, this study will visualize those reasons which may prove to be of assistance in garnering their resources.

2. The present need and objective of this study can be satisfied if it develops quantitatively and qualitatively, especially in search of new paradigms and bold individual and collective research ventures and integration with related social sciences.

3. The socio-political situation of the States of U.P. and Bihar is responsible for the underestimation of sports developmental trends in families. This study will for sure contribute towards this direction in understanding the reasons for underdevelopment in sports.

4. The value of this work embarking on the problems will be important above all due to the need to awaken and develop “a sociological imagination” in Indian society, a humanistic approach to matters related to sport, and also to formulate future hypotheses that would be useful for more advanced empirical studies.

5. In conclusion, this research project is designed to ‘get the ball rolling’ in the field of sport sociology in regard to the systematic examination of social movement theories in India, and other parts of the globe.

Language, cultural differences and expense are common downsides, but there are opportunities to learn new techniques, work in diverse settings and polish confidence. European Researchers can find a safe and more liberal research environment here in India, in the area of Sociology of Sports. Moving to a new country enables early-career researchers to gain fresh cultural and scientific perspectives. For many European Union scientists, a successful research project in India is also a springboard to a career in their home country and vice versa.

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ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА СТРАН-ЧЛЕНОВ ШОС В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ СФЕРЕ

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Аннотация: В данной статье авторы делают акцент на одну из важных ветвей в Шанхайской организации сотрудничества-постоянно действующей межгосударственной и международной организацией в сфере образования. Сотрудничество в культурно-гуманитарной сфере, которое способствует взаимопониманию между государствами – членами ШОС, а также укрепляет дружбу и политическое взаимное доверие, создавая благоприятные условия для формирования общих ценностей и культурной идентичности.

Ключевые слова: культурные ценности, Шанхайская организация сотрудничества, гуманитарное сотрудничество, культурная идентичность, Университет ШОС, система образования, образовательная интеграция, образование без границ.

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